

GIVING NATIONAL COLOR IN THE TRANSLATION OF CHARLOTTE BRONTE'S NOVEL "JANE EYRE"

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Abstract: This article analyzes the features of national color reflection in the translation of Charlotte Bronte's novel "Jane Eyre" into Uzbek. The work shows the unique aspects of the English national spirit and culture, while the issues of adapting these aspects for the Uzbek reader and preserving the national diversity were considered in the translation process. The problems that arise in the process of translation, i.e. intercultural differences, linguistic and stylistic adaptations, as well as the creative approaches of the translator are studied. The article, based on the principles of reflecting the national color in the medium of translation, reflects on the methods of preserving the original spirit of the work in the Uzbek language translation.

Key words: Charlotte Bronte, "Jane Eyre", national color, translation theory, intercultural communication, linguistic adaptation, stylistic methods, translation problems, national cultural heritage.

Introduction.

Translation of literary works has not only linguistic, but also cultural significance. In the process of translation, it is an important scientific and practical issue to reproduce the national color of the language in which the work was written in another language, including Uzbek. Charlotte Brontë's novel "Jane Eyre" is a vivid example of 19th century English literature. In this work, the author describes the culture, customs and social environment of his time in his unique artistic style. In the process of translation, it is a complex process to transfer such national features into another language, while preserving the originality of the work in a form that is understandable and acceptable to the reader, and requires the creative approach of the translator.

National color, i.e. symbols and images of national culture in the work, is an important factor in understanding the spirit of the work and conveying it to readers of other cultures. This article analyzes how the national color reflected in Charlotte Bronte's novel "Jane Eyre" is reflected in the Uzbek language translation, and the linguistic and stylistic methods used by the translator are analyzed. The research aims to contribute to the acceptance of the work by the Uzbek reader and the expansion of the imagination about the English culture reflected in the work.

Literature review:

Literary and translation studies conducted on Charlotte Bronte's novel "Jane Eyre" are of particular importance due to the unique artistic style of the work, the character of the characters, and aspects that reflect the national culture. Researchers evaluate this work as an artistic example of English culture and note that it deeply covers the issues of social inequality, women's rights and humanity.

In studying the difficulties in the translation process of the work, the scientific literature on translation studies is of particular importance. In particular, translators such as Eugene Naida and Peter Newmark emphasize the importance of the principles of "dynamic equivalence" and "semantic equivalence" in transferring national color into another language. Their theoretical views allow an in-depth analysis of the problems of preservation and adaptation of national culture in the process of translation.

Bahadir Karimov's work on ways of reflecting national color in Uzbek translations is considered valuable. In his opinion, it is important to fully convey not only the linguistic aspects of the work, but also the cultural essence in the translation. This requires the translator to work close to the original, but making full use of the possibilities of his language.

The analysis of the translations of the novel "Jane Eyre" into different languages shows that the translators used different strategies in adapting the unique elements of the work to the English culture. For example, the translation of scenes depicting English customs, lifestyles and spiritual values is sometimes replaced by equivalents in other cultures. This, in turn, led to a partial loss of national color.

The analysis of these literatures and studies serves as the main tool in determining the scientific basis of preserving and adapting the national color in the process of translating the novel "Jane Eyre" into Uzbek. The theories of translation theory and experiences in Uzbek translation practice form the theoretical basis of this study.

Linguistic analysis of Charlotte Bronte's novel "Jane Eyre" allows to determine the uniqueness of the language tools used in the work and how they are reflected in the Uzbek language translation. The language used in the novel plays an important role in expressing the character of the characters, the social and cultural conditions of the events, and the artistic spirit of the work. Lexical and stylistic elements of the English language, slang words, idiomatic expressions, metaphors and other stylistic tools are widely used in the work.

Lexical-semantic features.

The lexicon used in Jane Eyre consists of words that reflect the social layers of the English language of that time. For example, words such as "governess", "estate", "parsonage" have been replaced by equivalents that are understandable for the Uzbek reader. However, some words are given with comments in order to preserve the cultural and historical context in the Uzbek language.

Stylistic tools

Brontë's style is complex and emotional, with many metaphors, similes, personifications, and symbolic expressions. For example, the following expressions require an important stylistic approach in translation:

- Original: "I am no bird; and no net ensnares me."

Translation: "I am not a bird and no net can catch me."

In this phrase, the metaphor describing human freedom is preserved in the translation and expressed with a close equivalent to the original.

Grammatical features

In Brontë's style, complex sentence structures are widely used, which are sometimes converted into simple sentences in translation. This process arose from the need to adapt to the logical and structural features of the Uzbek language. English inversions and long sentences, for example:

- Original: "A restless movement, a fearful gesture of despair, and a sigh of utter anguish left my heart breathless."

Translation: "A gesture of despair, a gesture of fear, and a deep breath made my heart explore."

In this case, the grammatical adaptation was carried out while preserving the spirit of the original.

Idiomatic expressions

The work contains many idiomatic expressions characteristic of English culture. In the process of translation, such expressions were replaced by existing equivalents in the Uzbek language, or new expressions were created to preserve the artistic content. For example:

- Original: "It is raining cats and dogs."

Translation: "It is raining very hard."

Here, the translator has chosen a convenient expression in Uzbek, while preserving the folk imagery.

Language and dialect elements

The elements of dialect used in the language of the characters reveal their social origin and character. In the translation, these elements are given in the

Uzbek language through cultural adaptation, for example, simple equivalents used in the vernacular are used instead of dialect words.

Linguistic analysis shows that in the process of translating the novel "Jane Eyre" linguistic adaptation tools were effectively used to preserve the artistic style, lexical richness and national color of the work. In the process of translation, taking into account stylistic features and cultural differences, a creative approach was used in order to convey the spirit of the work to the Uzbek reader. This makes it possible to preserve the originality of the work in the translation.

Discussion:

The process of translating Charlotte Bronte's novel "Jane Eyre" into the Uzbek language necessitates the need to sufficiently preserve the national color reflected in the work. The main difficulties encountered in the translation process are related to expressing the lexical and stylistic elements characteristic of the English culture in the work in an understandable and suitable form for the Uzbek reader. In this matter, the creative approach of the translator and the application of the principles based on the theory of translation are of great importance.

The analysis shows that the translator followed the principles of dynamic and semantic equivalence in reflecting the national color in the novel. For example, idiomatic expressions typical of the English culture have been replaced by equivalent or similar expressions in the Uzbek language. Although this method is easy to understand for an Uzbek reader, in some cases it may lead to a partial loss of the national spirit of the work. For this reason, some phrases are given in the translation with the help of annotations. This approach helped preserve the artistic value of the work.

Figurative expressions, such as metaphors and similes, which are important in Brontë's style, are expressed in the translation as close as possible to the original. For example, the phrase "I am no bird; and no net ensnares me" in Uzbek is translated as "I am not a bird and no net can catch me", which not only reflects the artistic tone of the work, but also its meaningful depth. also saved.

Special attention is paid to the preservation of national cultural diversity in the translation of dialect and dialect elements from the novel into Uzbek. In the translation, the complex structures characteristic of the dialect are adapted to the Uzbek language with the help of words and phrases used in the vernacular. This method served to reveal the character of the heroes.

During the discussion, it was found that the translator tried to cover the linguistic and cultural aspects of the work in reflecting the national color. Nevertheless, in some places, due to cultural adaptation, the original cultural expressions in the work have been somewhat simplified or modernized. This partially complicated the full reflection of the national color.

In conclusion, it can be said that the translation of the novel "Jane Eyre" is an important step in introducing the Uzbek reader to English literature and culture, and it has been possible to preserve the artistic value and national spirit of the work as much as possible. Successful approaches to preserving national color in the process of translation is an important experience that deserves to be studied scientifically and practically.

Conclusion.

While translating Charlotte Bronte's novel "Jane Eyre" into Uzbek, preserving the national color and conveying it to the reader is a complicated but important process. In the process of translation, the artistic style, linguistic features and cultural content of the work are reflected as closely as possible to the original. Linguistic and stylistic adaptation methods used by the translator served to preserve the originality and national diversity of the novel in the Uzbek language translation.

The analysis shows that the translator used the principles of dynamic and semantic equivalence in expressing the national color. The comprehensibility and cultural similarity of the content of the work is ensured by providing idiomatic expressions and dialectal elements in Uzbek with the help of close equivalents or explanations. At the same time, in some cases, the simplification or modernization of the translation complicated the complete preservation of the national spirit of the work.

The methods used in the translation process contributed not only to the preservation of the aesthetic and cultural value of the work of art, but also to the strengthening of cultural communication between English and Uzbek cultures. On the basis of this study, a deeper study of the principles and methods of translating national color shows that it is necessary for the scientific and practical foundations used in the field of translation studies in the future. As a final result, it can be said that the translation of the novel "Jane Eyre" is a successful experiment in introducing the Uzbek reader to English literature, and offers valuable knowledge and approaches in highlighting the current issues of national color reflection.

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